

The Synergistic Integration of Rational and Emotional Dynamics in Brand Design and Development

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Abstract

Successful and enduring brands integrate a number of important core dynamics that reach far beyond the narrow confines of their functional utility. They are deeply rooted in human concerns, aspirations and emotions, and embody complex, densely packed sets of values and meanings. These values, or brand dynamics, are capable of evoking and conveying a wide range of facts and motivations, and contain rational and non-rational components that engender favourable emotional responses, or brand images, in customers' minds. Creating this 'emotional response' is what real brand design is all about. It is about designing and developing brands in a collaborative, synergistic manner so that their integrated whole becomes greater than the sum of their parts.

The aim of any successful brand development programme should be, therefore, to eliminate risk and optimally design and position brands so that they make their widest, most powerful emotional appeal to their respective customer group(s) from the outset.

This text explores these issues and describes a cross-disciplinary collaborative approach developed over time to help encourage corporations to design and market new brands in a manner that captures everything those brands are capable of standing for and meaning. By methodically auditing and evaluating the many rational and emotional dynamics that are capable of influencing consumer brand preference, and then configuring these dynamics in a synergistic manner so as to create unique, desirable and enduring brand images in customers' minds, the risk of commercial failure can be reduced.

Keywords: Brand, Design, Emotion, Function, Synergy

Introduction: Emotional drivers and brand motivation

"You can't beat the feeling"

Coca-Cola advertisement (Pendergrast 1994).

Successful consumer brands are extremely complex entities. The brand images they create, in other words the perceptual entity relating to the brand that will reside in the mind of the consumer, consist of complicated clusters of disparate dynamics integrated into a coherent whole. This whole, for successful brands at least, is usually greater than the sum of the parts because of powerful synergies that come into play.

So, what are these brand dynamics, and how can they be identified, classified and integrated in order to create successful and enduring brand images?

This text will attempt to define the main general core brand dynamics in terms of distinct fundamental values and also describe some of the specific and relevant emotional dynamics that have been identified in the literature. Brand dynamics capture important aspects of functional product performance, but more importantly, they also encompass relevant customer emotional needs. Using the approach defined, it should be possible to classify and distil all relevant and interrelated brand dynamics into a unique, simple and concise phrase or Core Brand Value that any given brand, and only that brand, will own.

Brand research has taken many forms to date, including research on brand image (Park, Jaworski, and MacInnis 1986; Reynolds and Gutman 1984), attitudes towards brands (Lutz 1975; Park and Young 1986), brand loyalty (Jacoby and Chestnut 1978; Reichheld 1996), brand equity (Aaker 1991; Baldinger 1990; Keller 1993), brand extensions (Smith and Park 1992), brand personality (Aaker 1997) and brand relationships (Chaudhuri and Holbrook 2001; Fournier 1998).

Although the role of emotion in branding and brand research has been previously discussed in the literature (Gordon 2002; Erevelles and Horton 1998; Gobé 2001; Alcock et al. 1987; Travis 2000), the true nature of the emotional dimensions that underpin brand relationships still remains far from clear.

Defining core brand dynamics

All core brand dynamics can, in general, be classified into one of three major groups:

Group 1: Core functional dynamics

Core Functional Dynamics are concerned with logical issues such as:

- *What does the brand 'really' do?*
- *How is the brand offered?*
- *Why is the brand needed?*
- *Why is the brand different?*

Group 2: Core need dynamics

Core Need Dynamics relate to emotional questions such as:

- *Which of the customer's psychological, motivational, situational or role needs does the brand satisfy?*
- *How does/will the customer feel about the brand?*
- *Is there a single overall need that the brand satisfies better than any other?*

Group 3: Core evaluative dynamics

Core Evaluative Components are concerned with questions such as:

- *With what quality or dynamic does the core function of the brand fulfil or satisfy the customer's core need?*
- *How can/will the brand be judged?*
- *On what evidence and against what standards can this judgment be made?*

The synergistic integration of these core dynamics will define the Core Brand Value for any given brand.

Combining a brand's core function and core user need to define its core utility

The first test of consistency between a brand's Core Function and the Core User Need it satisfies will be the ease with which both values can be expressed by the same single value so that a single word or phrase can credibly encompass both values to describe the brand's Core Utility or usefulness (Figure 1).

Figure 1, Brand Utility (conjoined expression of Function and Need) is determined by the actual Core Function of the brand and the Core User Need it satisfies.

All successful brands clearly identify the important user need they satisfy. Dominant market leaders, in particular, carve out a clear appeal encompassing an integrated expression of their core function in addition to the core user need they meet. This clarity, which goes beyond any mere functional claim, relates to both the brand's Core Function (rational dynamic) and the customer's Core Need (psychological/emotional dynamic). In this way, the Core Utility of the brand can be determined, communicated and in turn understood by the consumer. It is usually possible to determine the Core Utility of any credibly positioned brand. Failure or inability to do so usually means that there are inconsistencies at the very heart of a brand, often among those very individuals responsible for bringing the brand to market (including designers, marketers, market researchers. etc). Any such lack of clarity and direction will, consequently, inhibit everything from the creation of the new brand through to the development of its eventual marketing strategy and promotional campaign.

It is also important to recognise that a given Core Utility can sometime relate to an entire brand category. In other words, the Core Function of more than one competing brand may well satisfy, or partially satisfy, the same Core User Need. The Core Utility of more than one brand may therefore be common to some degree. This is not usually the case for a completely new product/brand, but it is often the case for 'me-too' brands. Therefore, in order to encourage customers to evaluate brands differently it becomes necessary to define

and offer the best and most powerful expression of a brand's chosen (albeit sometimes shared) utility.

Figure 2, Rational brand dynamic (Core Function), emotional brand dynamic (Core User Need) and evaluative brand dynamic (Core Evaluator) combine to define the Evaluated Utility (or Core Brand Value) of any given brand.

The core evaluative dynamic

The Core Evaluator is the standard by which the customer is invited to judge how well, and with what quality or dynamic, the Core Function of the brand fulfils his/her Core User Need. A carefully chosen Evaluator will allow a brand to appropriate to itself a Utility (the conjoined expression of Function and Need), by offering the most compelling way of satisfying it (Figure 2).

Determination of the core brand value

Phase 1: Systematic analysis of brand dynamics

The first phase of any brand analysis process involves a systematic analysis of all available facts, data and judgments about a given brand.

This process should involve all those stakeholders who have direct or significant indirect responsibility for the brand, including:

- Product Designers
- Marketing Managers
- Sales Managers
- Market Researchers
- End users
- Legal/Regulatory representatives

The task of the brand analysis team is to determine the Core Functional, Core User Need, Core Evaluative and other interrelated dynamics of the brand. The extent to which this is possible is heavily dependent on the relevance and pertinence of the views of those involved, and the quantity and quality of market research data available. Usually, marketing departments will have large quantities of data relating to the functional aspects of a brand. For innovative new brands, psychological background data and insight research is often incomplete and requires careful interpretation at this stage. If a brand is already a significant market leader, the psychological dynamics typically require particular attention.

Phase 2: Integration of the core brand dynamics into a coherent core brand value

Successful brands integrate these complex core dynamics into a single, coherent 'Core Brand Value'. For consumers, every aspect of a brand is related to everything else. They will experience and respond to the entire 'gestalt' of functional, emotional and evaluative components of the brand. The following schematic shows how these interrelated brand values are assigned to their respective positions on a 'brand map' which acts as both an aid to assimilation and as a double check on the appropriateness of linkages that will be made (Figure 3).

Figure 3, Brand Analysis model – facilitates the audit of all rational and emotional dynamics of a given brand, and distillation of these to extract a meaningful and enduring promotional platform.

Core function

At its most basic, abstract level, what is the key function that the brand delivers? What is it, and what does it do?

Core user need

Which customer need does the brand most powerfully satisfy?

Core evaluator

What quality of delivery will the brand offer to demonstrate that it best satisfies ALL the customer's needs?

Rational differentiation

What 'in-use' characteristics or effects differentiate the brand from other brands? What should the key features and benefits of the brand's sales story be?

Brand personality

What adjectives describe the desired personality of the brand? How does it behave? What is expected of it? The Brand Personality will be expressed through brand name creation, logo design, colour, typography, icon design, packaging, point of sale materials, etc.

Brand positioning

What does the brand do, and who does it do it for? How will the need satisfaction benefits offered by the brand be related to the customer's behaviour and aspirations? The Brand Positioning is a clear statement of where the client wants to compete in the market and the key customer segment needs which the company wants customers to believe the product will satisfy in a way that differentiates the brand from competitive products in the customers' minds.

In short it is a clear statement of:

- a: Where the brand should be used
- and*
- b: Why the brand should be used

Examples of generally accepted sentence structures for Brand Positioning Statements include:

- a: For [description of customer group], [brand] is a [frame of reference] that has/does [point of difference] because [overwhelming reason to believe].
- or*
- b: [Brand] is better than [define competitor] for [define target customer group(s)] because it [state main benefit] as a result of [evidence].

Product role

What is the most satisfying rational pay-off that the brand can deliver? Why is the brand important? The Product Role is a rational, functionally based expression of the Core Brand Value reflecting the rational values and dynamics of the brand. The Product Role will normally be communicated and expressed via education (as opposed to promotional) activities and PR as opposed to advertising and promotion.

Brand promise

What role will the brand play in the customer's life? Why is the brand important? The Brand Role is an overt emotion based expression of the Core Brand Value reflecting the psychological and emotional values and dynamics of the brand. The Brand Promise will normally be communicated and expressed via packaging design, advertising and promotion.

The holistic brand model makes use of both rational and emotional elements in identifying the factors that lead to brand relationships with consumers. Brand relationships include both rational and emotional elements and there are some dynamics that are an amalgam of both. As shall be described, the final factors in the holistic brand model facilitate the merging of emotion and reason, right and left brain hemispheres, feelings and thoughts, affects and cognitions.

Emotional drivers

How will the customer 'feel' about the brand? What insights are there into how the customer emotionally feels and behaves in this area? What are the emotional drivers that will influence brand motivation?

Although many emotional drivers have been identified in the literature, nine are briefly described here:

1: Approachability

This emotional driver is based on the ancient system of approach-avoidance that is innate in human beings. It has been suggested that uncertainty reduction in humans is a major explanation for the approach mechanism to select certain brands and avoid others. Because reduction of uncertainty is a rational activity usually characterized by information seeking (Berger and Calabrese 1975), and because reduction of uncertainty results in attraction and liking, the approachability driver consists of both rational and emotional bases.

Approachability has been defined it as "the outcome of a risk reduction process that is a positive feeling of willingness to obtain the brand" (Chaudhuri et al. 2002).

2: Curiosity

Cognitive affects, including curiosity, interest, and intrigue, function to educate the consumer through exploration of the brand. Learning about a brand leads to greater knowledge about, and thus a closer relationship with, it. Because this exploration is a pleasurable pursuit,

curiosity is an amalgam of both affective and cognitive outcomes. Thus curiosity has been defined as “a feeling of pleasurable exploration that results in a close relationship” (Chaudhuri et al. 2002). It is an approach mechanism based on a desire to get to know the brand better. Brand communication design will function here to produce the desired learning and also to create the feeling of curiosity and intrigue that leads to further exploration.

3: Empowerment

A brand may make the consumer feel a sense of empowerment as a result of the control it now offers the consumer in taking care of a particular problem. This in turn may make the consumer feel closer to the brand. This type of empowerment is not the absolute power of either consumer or brand but a shared power which often depends on communication for its effectiveness and continuance. The basis for this shared power is the furtherance of mutual goals (of both the consumer and the brand), leading to a close relationship.

It has been found that there is a cyclical relationship between a person’s rational beliefs about perceived control or empowerment and their behaviour (Schmitz and Skinner 1993). Thus, empowerment has been shown to have both a rational and an emotional base. Finally, there is evidence of its importance in the psychology literature in terms of constructs such as ‘desire for control’ (Thompson, Chaiken, and Hazlewood 1993) and ‘the need for power’ (Jenkins 1994). The empowerment driver has been defined as “a feeling of control, which enables the consumer to overcome day to day problems as a result of a brand relationship” (Chaudhuri et al. 2002).

4: Familiarity

Closeness in interpersonal relationships usually increases with time. Time allows for experience that leads to better knowledge (emotional and cognitive) or familiarity with the brand. Familiarity, in turn, leads to better prediction of brand performance and a feeling of greater closeness. Thus, relationships develop through communication over time. As in the case of trust, time also reduces uncertainty, and communication again leads to closeness.

Familiarity is viewed as both knowledge of the brand that the consumer is capable of describing (rational dynamics) and narrating in terms of product attributes etc, and also as knowledge of the brand gained through direct experience or acquaintance with the brand (emotional dynamics). Familiarity is thus an amalgam of both rational and emotional

dynamics. One is considered, thoughtful, sequential and linear; the other is instinctive, intuitive, holistic and spontaneous. The familiarity driver is a true amalgam of reason and emotion that has been described as “a feeling of knowledge about the brand” (Chaudhuri et al. 2002).

5: Identification

Identification refers to a sense of shared values between the consumer and the brand. In other words, the consumer feels that the brand reflects an image that is consistent with her or his own values, attitudes and identity. This attitudinal similarity in shared goals, values, etc. is described in the literature on interpersonal relations (Burleson and Denton 1992; Byrne 1971; Hatfield and Rapson 1992). In general, it is widely accepted that attitudinal similarity leads to attraction in relationships.

Identification begins with a cognitive understanding of values and results in emotional identification. Consumers may even be motivated to say that a brand and his/her self-concept are one and the same. It has been maintained that affects implicate the self and that affective judgments describe “something that is in ourselves” (Zajonc 1980). Accordingly, the identification driver has both rational and emotional meanings. The identification driver has been defined as “a feeling of similarity with the brand and its social meaning in terms of values and attitudes”(Dumont 2003). It is also important to note that communication is a significant factor in the similarity-attraction relationship (Duck and Barnes 1992). Thus, effective and emotional brand communication, which depicts prevalent social values, will result in feelings of identification with the brand.

6: Pride

Owners of certain status brands often feel pride in their ownership of those brands while, conversely, consumers who do not own them may express envy because of their non-ownership of those brands. Pride and envy have been described as emotional drivers arising mainly out of the expectations of others (Buck 1999). Consumers may feel pride of ownership in that by owning the brand they meet and even exceed the expectations of themselves and of significant others. From not owning the brand and, thus, not meeting the expectations of others, consumers may feel envy, shame, etc. Envy, in turn, may often lead to a greater desire for closeness with the brand.

7: Relevance

One notion of relevance is related to the notion of involvement defined in the marketing literature as “the relevance of the product to the needs and values of the consumer” (Zaichkowsky 1985). However, another notion of relevance refers to involvement with the brand, and has been defined as “a feeling of involvement with the brand as a result of the brand’s importance and emotional fit in the life of the consumer” (Chaudhuri et al. 2002).

There may be a reciprocal connection between relevance and a consumer’s close relationship with a brand. In other words, as the rational and emotional bases of involvement increase, the relationship becomes closer; and, as the relationship becomes closer, the involvement with the brand also increases. The two would seem to be almost inseparable.

Communication is the element that maintains this reciprocal connection and fosters the growth of the relationship. In addition to advertising, there are many other activities in which a brand also can engage with its customers. For example, financial institution sponsor music concerts and automobile companies foster outdoor events that increase the relevance of their brands in the life and lifestyle of the consumer. Moreover, brand managers can attempt to introduce the brand into the community or ‘village’ in which consumers already owe allegiance (Oliver 1999; Klein 2001), thereby increasing the relevance of the brand to the individual consumer.

8: Trust

Trust usually leads to intimacy and a close relationship. Two aspects of trust are identified in the literature (Doney and Cannon 1997; Sirdeshmukh, Singh, and Sabol 2002): the notion of benevolence in the brand, and the notion of faith in the ability of the brand to perform an expected function. Faith in the brand translates into feelings of reliability, safety and honesty. Although trust may include calculative processes (consideration of the rewards and cost of the relationship, for example), it has sufficient affective underpinnings to be termed a ‘cognitive’ emotion or affect. It is a subjective feeling derived from both emotion and cognition. Accordingly, and in consonance with the literature (Chaudhuri and Holbrook 2001; Moorman, Zaltman, and Deshpande 1992; Morgan and Hunt 1994), trust has been defined as “a feeling of faith in the reliability of the brand to perform its stated function” (Chaudhuri et al. 2002). Interestingly, the literature cites trust as most relevant in situations or environments of uncertainty in which the person feels especially vulnerable (Moorman, Zaltman, and Deshpande 1992; Doney and Cannon 1997). In circumstances where

significant functional differences exist between brands in a given product category and perceptions that there could be significant risk involved in selecting the wrong brand (i.e. as in pharmaceutical products), the notion of trust may have special relevance (Chaudhuri 1998). Once again, communication design usually plays a key role in establishing brand relationships.

9: Warmth

Warmth signifies a combination of love, desire and intimacy dimensions, merged into one driver. Intimacy is based on love and so denotes desire in the pro-social sense. So, the notion of love may function as the recurring theme in the warmth dimension. But what is love? Love has been described as being as ‘a happy surprise’ (Berscheid 1983). It is a happy but unexpected interruption in our lives. Love, thus, includes other affective states such as positive surprise as well as attachment, affiliation and liking. Related to love is the notion of delight in consumer relationships, and a literature on this notion is emerging (Oliver, Rust, and Varki 1997; Rust and Oliver 2000).

Warmth is “...a positive feeling involving physiological arousal and precipitated by experiencing a relationship of love with a brand” (Aaker, Stayman, and Hagerty 1986). Overall, the warmth driver is the repository of a number of positive emotional and affective consequences arising out of the consumer’s relationship with the brand. Positive moods, such as warmth, have been found to generate more positive attitudes and thoughts towards brands (Petty et al. 1993) and also greater liking for an advertisement and increased likelihood of purchase (Aaker, Stayman, and Hagerty 1986; De Pelsmacker and Guens 1999).

It is important to stress that emotional drivers, although interrelated, are still independent. So, for example, some degree of trust is usually engendered by feelings of love, but it is certainly possible to love someone or something without trusting it to the same degree. Love, trust, pride, curiosity, etc. are related to each other but they are not the same thing, either conceptually or empirically. Thus, it is important to deliberately create both love and trust, for instance, if that is the emotional position sought for the brand. Simply creating love may not create pride, trust, familiarity, etc.

Since certain basic emotions (happiness, sadness, anger, fear, surprise, disgust) can be recognised by people regardless of their culture (Ekman and Friesen 1975), it has been

suggested that emotions are universal in their language, despite the fact that cultures may vary on the understanding of cognitions and thoughts, which are highly dependent on cultural variations of language (Frutiger 1989). There are many other reasons for considering emotion in relation to brand design and communication. Emotion is processed more speedily, for example, and may remain more consistently in the mind than cognition. Moreover, determined competitors can easily copy cognitive claims while emotional appeals are very difficult to imitate successfully. Furthermore, imitations can easily be mistaken for variations on the original emotional theme thereby unintentionally increasing the original brand's share of mind (Mullen 1979).

Facilitating common understanding across brand development teams

A correctly observed brand analysis process involves a lot of hard work and can be heavy going. However, the entire process is normally redeemed by the satisfaction experienced as each phase is completed and the functional and emotional territory truly occupied by the brand is revealed. The need to generate the deepest possible understanding of, and attitudes towards, the brand is overriding. All existing results of quantitative and qualitative research will need to be taken into account and become part of any new promotional campaign that will, in turn, need to express a clear, motivating, selling idea in a form that customers will notice, talk about and act upon

This forcing of clarity on the plethora of available data is what lies at the heart of the brand analysis process. What is excluded will be as important as what is included. The process is rigorous and the resulting Core Brand Value should be specific enough to be expressed and communicated clearly between all those involved in the design and promotion of the brand.

Conclusion

Brands themselves do not have emotions, only the ability (through strategies like product design, packaging design, advertising etc.) to create them within consumers. Accordingly, brand professionals should strive to elicit these affects through the application of design. Thus, for instance, status appeals contribute to pride and envy; providing different types of knowledge about the brand can create familiarity; and depicting the reliability of the brand can generate trust. The multidimensional nature of the brand model described in this text

offers a variety of new emotional positioning opportunities for brand professionals. The brand model allows brand designers and managers to engender emotional brand feelings and sentiments instead of offering purely rational explanations of product differentiation. In today's high-technology world where unique product attributes are rare and rapidly copied or improved on by competitors, sustained emotional positioning offers the distinct and important advantage that it cannot be copied successfully by competitors without further reinforcing the original brand's standing in the consumer's mind. These rational and emotional amalgams are anchored in the literature on relationship development in interpersonal communication and social psychology. Accordingly, it can be expected that the successful and synergistic integration of the dynamics in the brand model described will have lasting, long-term effects.

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